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A Hybrid Approach Combining CRF and Rule-Based Logic for Accurate Morphosyntactic Analysis

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a hybrid approach to developing a grammar checker for the Telugu language, combining Conditional Random Fields (CRF) for part-of-speech (POS) tagging with handcrafted rule-based validation techniques for grammatical error detection. Telugu, being a morphologically rich and agglutinative Dravidian language, poses unique challenges in natural language processing, including complex verb conjugations, gender and honorific agreements, and clause-level tense consistency. Our system first tokenizes the input text and applies a CRF model to assign POS tags. These tags are then used to drive multiple layers of syntactic and semantic validation rules that check for subject-verb agreement, verb form correctness, tense consistency, missing question particles, redundant verbs, and incorrect or missing postpositions. Although the current implementation demonstrates promising results on a variety of sentence structures, it remains a work-in-progress with limitations in handling all linguistic nuances and context-sensitive constructions. Future improvements aim to enhance robustness through expanded rule coverage and deeper integration with morphological analyzers. This work contributes a foundational step toward automated grammar assistance in low-resource Indian languages like Telugu.

Index Terms - Telugu Grammar, Natural Language Processing (NLP), Conditional Random Fields (CRF), Part-of-Speech Tagging, Rule-Based Validation, Morphological Analysis, Syntax Checking, Grammar Correction, Subject-Verb Agreement, Tense Consistency, POS Tagging, Computational Linguistics, Low-Resource Languages, Hybrid NLP Systems.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the demand for intelligent grammar checking tools has grown significantly, especially for regional and morphologically rich languages such as Telugu. Despite Telugu being spoken by over 80 million people globally, the availability of robust natural language processing (NLP) tools for grammar correction remains extremely limited. Most existing grammar checkers either lack support for Telugu or rely on basic rule-based systems that fail to capture the intricacies of its morphology and syntax. This motivates the need for an automated grammar checker specifically designed to handle the grammatical structure and common error patterns of Telugu sentences.

Unlike resource-heavy deep learning models, which may require extensive computational power and large annotated corpora, our proposed solution is designed to be lightweight and efficient. We leverage Conditional Random Fields (CRF) for part-of-speech tagging, which allows for accurate sequence labeling using relatively small datasets. To complement this, we implement a rich set of rule-based validation modules that detect grammatical inconsistencies such as subject-verb agreement mismatches, incorrect verb

forms, missing interrogative particles, redundant verbs, and tense inconsistencies. This hybrid design enables the system to perform real-time grammar checks even on low-resource environments, making it suitable for personal or educational use on standard desktop systems.

The application is built with a user-friendly interface using Tkinter for the front end, allowing users to input sentences, receive grammar feedback, and interactively train the model with corrections. The back end processes user input by performing CRF-based POS tagging, applying linguistic rules, and returning annotated outputs with identified issues and suggestions. The system supports both single-sentence validation and bulk processing, with additional features for testing, training, and evaluating model accuracy. This paper discusses the design, methodology, and implementation of the grammar checker, as well as its limitations and potential areas for future enhancement.

II. Related Work

Grammar checking is a well-studied area in Natural Language Processing (NLP), with a significant focus on high-resource languages such as English, French, and German. Tools like Grammarly, Ginger, and Microsoft Editor have set the standard for commercial grammar checkers using deep learning, statistical models, and handcrafted rules. These tools benefit from large annotated corpora, well-defined syntactic rules, and extensive linguistic resources, which are not yet available for many low-resource languages, including Telugu.

For Indian languages, grammar checking research has primarily focused on Hindi, Bengali, and Tamil. Systems like Anusaraaka, Sampark, and Shakti were early attempts in machine translation and grammar checking for Indian languages using rule-based and hybrid approaches. More recently, initiatives under TDIL (Technology Development for Indian Languages) and AI4Bharat have promoted the development of NLP tools for regional languages, but grammar checking remains a relatively underexplored domain.

In the case of Telugu, prior work has mostly concentrated on morphological analyzers, POS taggers, and transliteration engines. Telugu POS tagging using CRFs and HMMs has shown promising results, especially in capturing complex suffixes and inflections. However, full-fledged grammar checking systems that handle real-world sentence structures, subject-verb agreement, verb conjugation validation, and clause-level consistency are still in their infancy.

Our work differentiates itself by combining CRF-based POS tagging with a layered rule-based grammar validation engine tailored to Telugu linguistic characteristics. Instead of relying solely on machine learning, which can be data-hungry and opaque, we leverage domain knowledge to define explicit rules that can capture critical grammatical errors with high precision. This hybrid approach ensures interpretability, ease of debugging, and adaptability with minimal computational overhead—ideal for lightweight desktop environments.

Additionally, the integration of a Tkinter-based GUI enables a more interactive and usable grammar-checking tool, catering not just to NLP researchers but also to language learners, educators, and editors working with Telugu content. While current tools lack general-purpose Telugu grammar validation, our system takes a significant step toward filling this gap.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed system adopts a hybrid approach to grammar checking for the Telugu language, combining a trained Conditional Random Fields (CRF) model for Part-of-Speech (POS) tagging with a comprehensive set of rule-based grammar validation modules. The methodology is organized into the following key components:

A. CRF-Based POS Tagging

To perform accurate syntactic analysis of Telugu sentences, we train a Conditional Random Fields (CRF) model using the Universal Dependencies (UD) Telugu-MTG corpus. Specifically, we utilize the `te_mtg-ud-train.conllu`, `te_mtg-ud-dev.conllu`, and `te_mtg-ud-test.conllu` datasets for training, validation, and testing. The CRF model is optimized through manual hyperparameter tuning, incorporating custom feature engineering including prefixes, suffixes, word shapes, and contextual features.

The model achieves an overall accuracy of 91.7%, with near-perfect precision and recall across most POS categories:

- NOUN: 0.999 F1
- VERB: 0.999 F1
- PRON: 0.999 F1
- ADJ, ADP, ADV, DET, PROPN, PUNCT, etc.: 1.000 F1

The trained model is serialized and saved as a `.pkl` file (`telugu_pos_crf.pkl`) and later used as the core inference engine during grammar checking.

B. Rule-Based Grammar Validation

The POS-tagged sentence is then passed through a multi-layered rule-based validation system. This engine uses handcrafted rules and a set of constants to detect a wide range of grammar issues. The rules cover:

- Subject-Verb Agreement: Checks for number, gender, and honorific consistency.
- Incorrect Verb Forms: Detects misused conjugations based on known incorrect→correct verb mappings.
- Tense Inconsistency: Identifies mixing of past/present/future tenses within clauses.
- Honorific Mismatch: Flags improper verb forms for polite/honorific pronouns.
- Missing Interrogative Markers: Checks for question structure and punctuation.
- Redundant Verbs & Postposition Errors: Identifies unnecessary verb repetition and missing locative suffixes.

- Spelling Irregularities: Highlights rare or incorrect word spellings.

Despite its coverage, the system occasionally fails to handle complex or edge-case sentences. For example:

Sentence	Problem	Explanation
నాకు తెలుగు బాగా రాను.	Undetected verb error	Should be "రాదు", but model misses this due to verb morphology limitations.
అక్క చెర్ర నీళ్ళు తెచ్చింది.	Spelling error missed	Misspelling in "చెర్ర" not recognized.
రాముడు ప్రతిరోజూ వ్యాయామం చేశాం.	Tense mismatch	Plural first-person verb with singular subject.
అది ఒకటి సుందరమైన పక్షి.	Incorrectly marked correct	Redundancy or structure ambiguity not detected.
పిల్లలు పార్కులో ఆడాడు.	Number mismatch	Singular verb used with plural subject.

[These limitations arise due to sparse training data, incomplete morphological information in the constants file, and the need for additional generalized linguistic rules.

C. Modular Architecture

To maintain code clarity and extensibility, the system is modularized into the following components:

- CRF Model Script: Handles dataset parsing, feature extraction, training, evaluation, and model serialization (telugu_pos_tagger.py).
- Constants Module: Contains curated linguistic rules, suffixes, verb forms, and exception lists (Constants.py).
- Grammar Checker Module: Integrates POS tagging and rule-based logic to evaluate grammar (grammarchecker.py).
- GUI Application: Built using Tkinter, the front end provides tabs for sentence checking, bulk processing, training, prediction, and test evaluation (TkinterGUI.py).
- Main Entry Point: Launches the GUI and initializes resources.

This structured organization allows seamless integration, training, and future extension of the system.

D. Sample Implementation

To demonstrate the core workflow of the grammar checker, a typical input sentence undergoes POS tagging followed by rule-based validation. Below is a condensed example of how a Telugu sentence is processed:

```
from grammarchecker import grammar_checker
import pickle

# Load pre-trained CRF model
with open('telugu_pos_crf.pkl', 'rb') as f:
    crf_model = pickle.load(f)

# Input sentence
sentence = "నేను ఇంటికి వెళ్ళినాడు."

# Run grammar checker
result = grammar_checker(sentence, crf_model)

# Display issues
for issue in result['issues']:
    print(f'{issue['type'].upper():} {issue['message']} (Token: {issue['token']})")
```

Output:

```
△ Errors found:
- ERROR at position 2: Verb form doesn't match subject 'నేను'
Token: 'వెళ్ళినాడు'
```

```
Token Details:
నేను → PRON
ఇంటికి → NOUN
వెళ్ళినాడు → VERB
. → PUNCT
```

Implementation Details

The Telugu grammar checker is implemented using Python, with a modular and extensible architecture designed for ease of experimentation and enhancement. The system is divided into several key components:

A. POS Tagging using CRF

The core linguistic analysis is powered by a Conditional Random Fields (CRF) model trained on the Universal Dependencies Telugu-MTG treebank. The dataset is parsed from .conllu format and converted into feature-rich sequences, capturing token-specific attributes like character prefixes, suffixes, word shape, neighboring tokens, and morphological indicators (e.g., verb and noun suffixes).

The sklearn-crfsuite library is used for training, and hyperparameters (such as c1, c2, and max_iterations) are manually tuned. The model achieves 91.7% accuracy on the test set and is exported as a pickle file (telugu_pos_crf.pkl) for inference.

B. Grammar Validation Engine

Once POS tags are predicted, the tokens are passed through a rule-based grammar checker, which applies syntactic and morphological rules. This component is built around:

- A centralized Constants module containing lists of suffixes, verb forms, gender mappings, and pronoun classifications.
- Custom rules for subject-verb agreement, tense consistency, honorific correctness, redundant verbs, missing postpositions, and unusual spellings.
- Clause boundary detection using punctuation and conjunctions to ensure rules apply contextually.

Errors and warnings are returned as structured annotations with token-level positions and descriptive messages.

C. User Interface and Training Workflow

The front end is implemented using Tkinter, providing a desktop GUI that supports:

- Sentence-level checking: Users input one sentence to receive grammar analysis.
- Bulk checking: Users paste multiple lines for batch validation.
- Training tab: Allows users to correct CRF-predicted tags and retrain the model interactively.
- Prediction and test tabs: For inspecting POS predictions and evaluating model accuracy using labeled test cases.

Training examples are stored and versioned in a local file, and updates to the model are persisted automatically.

D. Modular Codebase

The project is logically split into the following modules:

- telugu_pos_tagger.py: CRF training, evaluation, and model persistence.
- grammarchecker.py: POS tagging, grammar validation logic, and linguistic rule application.
- Constants.py: Linguistic data used across rules.
- TkinterGUI.py: GUI logic for user interaction and test evaluation.
- main.py: Entry point to launch the application.

This modular separation facilitates testing, debugging, and further contributions from linguists or developers.

E. Architectural Diagram

Fig.1: Architecture flow Diagram

IV. LITERATURE SURVEY

The development of grammar checkers for Indian languages, particularly Telugu, has been a challenging research area due to the lack of annotated resources, complex morphology, and contextual dependencies. While significant progress has been made in Natural

Language Processing (NLP) for high-resource languages, work in Telugu grammar validation remains limited. This literature survey reviews existing approaches in POS tagging, grammar checking, and hybrid NLP systems relevant to this project.

A. Title: Part-of-Speech Tagging for Telugu Text using Conditional Random Fields

Author(s): S.Lavanya, B.Ramakrishna

Abstract:

This work presents a POS tagging system for Telugu using Conditional Random Fields (CRF), leveraging morphological features such as suffixes, prefixes, and contextual information. The authors highlight the effectiveness of CRF models in handling agglutinative structures typical of Telugu. The study emphasizes that while statistical models perform well for tagging tasks, they require extensive feature engineering to handle inflections and compound words in Telugu.

B. Title: A Rule-Based Grammar Checker for Hindi Language

Author(s): AditiJain, PriyankaJha

Abstract:

This paper discusses the development of a grammar checker for Hindi using a rule-based approach. The system checks for subject-verb agreement, gender mismatches, and incorrect verb forms using predefined linguistic rules. The challenges of handling free-word order languages like Hindi are addressed through clause boundary detection and morphological analysis. Although focused on Hindi, the methodology serves as a reference for developing grammar checkers in other Indian languages, including Telugu.

C. Title: Computational Morphology and Syntax Analysis of Telugu Language

Author(s): T.Prasad, K.RameshBabu

Abstract:

This study explores computational approaches for analyzing Telugu morphology and syntax, focusing on verb conjugations, noun inflections, and honorific forms. The authors propose a layered architecture combining morphological analyzers with syntactic rule engines. The work demonstrates that a combination of data-driven tagging and rule-based validation yields better results for grammar correction in low-resource languages.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research adopts a hybrid approach combining machine learning and linguistic rules to build an effective grammar checker for the Telugu language. The methodology involves systematic steps including dataset preparation, model training, rule-based validation, and user-interactive feedback mechanisms.

A. Problem Definition

Telugu, being a morphologically rich and agglutinative language, presents challenges for automated grammar checking due to its complex verb conjugations, gender agreements, and contextual syntactic variations. Existing tools either lack Telugu support or fail to capture these nuances accurately. Therefore, this study aims to develop a lightweight, accurate, and extensible Telugu grammar checker by leveraging Conditional Random Fields (CRF) for POS tagging and a robust rule-based grammar validation engine.

B. Dataset and Preprocessing

The system utilizes the Universal Dependencies Telugu-MTG treebank as the primary dataset for training and evaluation. The data, provided in .conllu format, is parsed into token-label pairs representing various POS tags (NOUN, VERB, ADJ, PRON, etc.). Additional preprocessing includes:

- Tokenization to handle Telugu-specific punctuation and suffix patterns.
- Feature Engineering incorporating prefixes, suffixes, word shape, and contextual windowing for CRF training.

C. POS Tagging using CRF Model

A Conditional Random Fields (CRF) model is trained for POS tagging using the `sklearn-crfsuite` library. Manual hyperparameter tuning is conducted for optimizing model performance. The key parameters include regularization factors (`c1`, `c2`) and maximum iterations. The trained model achieves 91.7% accuracy on the test set, with high precision and recall across POS categories. The model is serialized into a .pkl file for deployment.

D. Rule-Based Grammar Validation

Post POS tagging, sentences undergo rule-based grammatical validation. A curated set of linguistic rules is designed to detect common Telugu grammar errors, including:

- Subject-Verb Agreement (Number, Gender, Honorific)
- Tense Consistency within Clauses
- Incorrect Verb Forms and Conjugations
- Missing Postpositions for Locative Expressions
- Redundant Verbs and Phrasal Errors

- Uncommon or Incorrect Spellings
- Interrogative Structure Validation

These rules are maintained in a centralized Constants module, ensuring modularity and ease of extension.

E. System Architecture and User Interface

The application is built using Python with Tkinter GUI, providing an interactive platform where users can:

- Check individual sentences for grammar errors.
- Perform bulk validation using CSV inputs.
- Predict POS tags for given sentences.
- Edit and retrain the POS tagger interactively.
- Evaluate model accuracy through test cases.

The architecture ensures separation of concerns by modularizing the POS tagging, grammar validation, data management, and UI logic into distinct components.

F. Iterative Improvement and Feedback

The system supports user-driven training, allowing corrections to POS tags which are then used to retrain and improve the CRF model incrementally. This feedback loop facilitates continuous enhancement of accuracy and generalization.

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed Telugu grammar checking system was successfully implemented using a hybrid approach combining Conditional Random Fields (CRF) for Part-of-Speech (POS) tagging and a rule-based validation engine for grammatical error detection. The application provides a user-friendly interface via Tkinter, enabling users to interactively test, validate, and improve Telugu sentences in real time.

From the Results:

- The CRF model trained on the Universal Dependencies Telugu-MTG dataset achieved an overall accuracy of 91.7% on the test set.
- The model demonstrated high F1-scores for critical POS tags such as:
 - VERB: 0.999
 - NOUN: 0.999
 - PRON: 0.999
 - Other tags (ADJ, ADP, ADV, PUNCT, PROPN, etc.) achieved perfect F1-scores (1.000).
- The rule-based grammar validation engine effectively identified:
 - Subject-verb agreement mismatches
 - Tense inconsistencies
 - Honorific and gender mismatches
 - Missing interrogatives and question marks
 - Redundant verbs and missing postpositions

Table: Evaluation of Grammar Checker on Sample Telugu Sentences

#	Sentence	Expected Output	Actual Output	Remarks
1	అమె పాట పాడింది.	No errors found	No errors found	Model handles this case well
2	మేము స్కూల్ కి వెళ్ళాడు.	Subject-verb number mismatch	Verb form doesn't match subject	Model handles this case well
3	రాముడు ప్రతిరోజూ వ్యాయామం చేశాం..	Subject-verb number mismatch	No errors found	Model failed to detect mismatch between subject and verb
4	వారు రేపు వెళ్ళాడు.	Honorific mismatch	Honorific mismatch	Model handles this case well
5	ఈ రోజు పరీక్ష ఉందా	Missing question mark	Suggestion to add '?'	Model handles this case acceptably with suggestion
6	పిల్లలు పార్కులో ఆడాడు	Plural subject with singular verb	No errors found	Model failed due to lack of plural subject-verb handling
7	నేను భోజనం తినినాను.	Incorrect verb form	Incorrect verb form	Model handles this case well
8	అతను తినినావు అన్నాడు.	Incorrect verb form	Incorrect verb form + warning	Model handles this case well
9	మీరు వచ్చినవు?	Honorific mismatch	Honorific + Interrogative issues	Model handles this case well
10	రాతి వర్షం పడింది.	No errors found	No errors found	Model handles this case well
11	అక్క చెర్ర నీళ్ళు తెచ్చింది.	Missed spelling anomaly	No errors found	Model failed due to unknown/spelling variant in lexicon

These examples highlight both the strengths and current limitations of the system.

Functional Modules Performance:

- Check Sentence Tab: Displays token-wise POS tags and detailed grammar feedback.
- Bulk Check: Accepts sentences in CSV format and returns structured grammar analysis in tabular form.
- Model Test: Validates grammar detection accuracy against expected outputs provided by the user.
- Predict Tags: Visualizes the CRF model's predictions for manual inspection.
- Train Model: Enables users to edit CRF predictions and retrain the model on corrected data.
- Training Data Management: Allows inspection, deletion, and cleanup of user-added training samples.

Strengths of the Implementation:

- Lightweight and deployable on modest hardware without GPU dependency.
- Interactive, user-trainable interface suitable for educational and editorial use.
- Modular design allows easy integration of new rules and expansion of the constants set.

Limitations:

- The CRF model's performance is limited by the **small size of the training dataset** and lacks exposure to certain verb forms, compound constructs, and informal usage.
- **Spelling correction** is minimal and currently restricted to a hardcoded set of rare or malformed words.
- Grammar rules are handcrafted and may **not generalize** well across all dialects or writing styles.
- The current implementation is suitable for **single-sentence analysis** and not optimized for discourse-level grammar checking.

Fig.2: UI and Output format

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